

IT323 - BUSINESS INTELLIGENCE

**UNDERSTANDING USER SATISFACTION THROUGH SENTIMENT AND
FEATURE-BASED SENTIMENT ANALYSIS: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF GRAB
AND UBER RIDE-HAILING SUPER APP REVIEWS ON GOOGLE PLAY STORE
USING PYTHON AND RAPIDMINER**

Submitted by:

**BALABA, MARK LOUIE O.
MACA, MARY GRACE R.
REYES ELIZA JANE C.**

Submitted to:

PROF. JONATHAN M. CABALLERO

Submission Date:

MAY 22, 2025

ABSTRACT

User satisfaction is defined as the comfortability or contentment of the end-users of an application (Trymata & Trymata, 2024). This study investigates user satisfaction with two major ride-hailing applications, Grab and Uber, by analyzing 1,000 English-language Google Play Store reviews for each app, written in December 2024. Using Python and RapidMiner, sentiment analysis was conducted with the VADER technique to classify reviews as positive, neutral, or negative. Word clouds of positive and negative reviews for both applications were also done to reveal the common themes in user reviews. Feature-based sentiment analysis was also applied to evaluate user feedback on specific app features, with results visualized through bar charts and tables. Findings revealed that Uber received more positive reviews and fewer complaints than Grab. While users valued Grab's multifunctionality and affordability, they frequently reported technical issues and poor customer service. Uber was praised for its performance, interface, and professional drivers, though concerns about pricing and availability were noted. The study concludes that user satisfaction is shaped by reliability, responsiveness, and app performance.

Keywords: *Grab, Uber, User Satisfaction, Sentiment Analysis*

INTRODUCTION

Background / Objectives

In today's technological age, almost anything can be accessible through mobile applications. They became important parts of our lives that were labeled as "places of public accommodation." This is one of the reasons why businesses often create mobile applications not only to offer their products and services but also to build brand loyalty and keep close contact with their customers (Froehlich, 2024). These businesses make their services available to everyone to help them with their everyday needs and demands. Among these businesses are Grab and Uber, which started as ride-hailing platforms helping every commuter's transportation needs. Now, they are already considered super-apps, offering services such as rides, food and package delivery, and even financial services.

Grab and Uber are two of the most well-known ride-hailing applications that transformed urban transportation through smartphone technology. Uber was founded in 2009 in San Francisco and quickly expanded worldwide. Grab began in 2012 in Malaysia as "My Teksi" and grew into Southeast Asia's leading Super App. Both offer ride-hailing, food delivery, digital payments, and logistics services. Their rivalry in Southeast Asia ended in 2018 when Uber sold its operations to Grab, solidifying Grab's performance in the region. Despite this, Uber remains active globally. With over 100 million downloads for Grab and 500 million for Uber,

reviews on platforms like the Google Play Store provide key insights into app performance, user experience, and overall satisfaction.

This study aims to analyze and compare user satisfaction with Grab and Uber based on the Google Play Store reviews written in English in December 2024. It examines user sentiments to identify key factors influencing satisfaction, such as app performance, usability, service quality, and customer support. By comparing positive and negative feedback, the study highlights each platform's strengths and weaknesses from the user's perspective. The research is limited to publicly available reviews on Google Play and does not include surveys, interviews, or data from other platforms. As a result, findings may be subjected to bias depending on the subjectivity of user experiences and potentially exaggerated reviews.

METHODS

Data Collection and Cleaning

User reviews for Grab and Uber were collected from the Google Play Store using Python's "google-play-scraper" and processed with pandas, resulting in 1,000 English-language reviews per app from December 2024. These served as the dataset for analyzing user satisfaction. To prepare the data, several preprocessing steps were applied: (a) converting text to lowercase; (b) removing punctuations, numbers, special characters, and stopwords; and (c) reducing words to their base form. These cleaning processes ensured consistency and

eliminated noise, allowing for more accurate text mining and sentiment analysis.

Sentiment Analysis

Sentiment Analysis is an approach to natural language processing (NLP) that identifies the emotional tone behind a body of text (Gillis & Barney, 2024). Sentiment Analysis was conducted using RapidMiner to classify Grab and Uber users as positive, negative, or neutral based on emotional tone. A lexicon-based method using the VADER model was applied, which assigns sentiment scores by matching words to a predefined dictionary. This approach was chosen for its efficiency and interpretability, suitable for the dataset's size and nature. The analysis sets the VADER model through the "Extract Sentiment" operator, generates a "Score" attribute, and assigns sentiment labels using conditional logic. Reviews with a score above 0 were labeled "Positive", below 0 as "Negative", and 0 as "Neutral". The results were visualized using a bar chart, allowing a clear comparison of user sentiment distribution between the two applications and providing insight into overall user satisfaction.

To explore the core themes of user satisfaction and dissatisfaction, this study applied the Term Occurrences technique to the textual reviews of Grab and Uber. Term Occurrences examine how often a term appears in a dataset. It helps in understanding and identifying what the users are commonly talking about positively and negatively on each application. The results of this analysis were visualized using color-coded word clouds, generated from wordclouds.com. Each application has a positive and a negative word cloud. The positive word cloud was colored in green, and the negative word cloud was colored in red. This visual approach helped reveal the most frequent themes in user feedback and provided a clear understanding of what users typically appreciate or criticize in the two applications.

Feature-Based Sentiment Analysis

This study used feature-based sentiment analysis to understand how Grab and Uber application features affect user satisfaction. Feature-based Sentiment Analysis is an NLP task that aims to identify and extract the sentiment of specific components of a product (*Papers With Code* -

Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA), n.d.). There are six main features that we focused on, including booking experience, payment methods, GPS accuracy, application responsiveness, customer support, and driver quality. A list of related keywords for each feature was manually created to reflect how users typically describe them. Five Excel files were used in this analysis, four of which contain positive and negative wordlists from the users' reviews on Google Play Store, and the other one contains the feature-keyword mappings. We used Power BI to link the keywords to the right features. Python with Pandas was also used to clean the data and remove the duplicates, as well as to count how often each keyword appeared in a positive or negative review of users. These counts were summarized in a table to present the number of positive and negative mentions in each application.

Comparative Analysis

Throughout the analysis, results from each data processing stage were presented in parallel for both applications to highlight their similarities and differences in user sentiment, experiences, and expectations. This comparative approach ensures a balanced and detailed evaluation of user satisfaction, aligned with the study's reviews.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Sentiment Analysis

Figure 1: Sentiment Analysis of user reviews for Grab and Uber

Sentiment analysis showed that Uber received more positive reviews (708) than Grab (557), suggesting higher overall user satisfaction and a more consistent experience. Grab, however, had

significantly more negative reviews (264) compared to Uber (159), indicating greater user frustration—often related to app usability, customer service, pricing, and technical issues. Neutral feedback followed a similar trend, with Grab receiving 245 and Uber 150. These neutral reviews often reflected mixed experiences or technical suggestions, hinting at uncertainty or inconsistency in Grab’s performance. Overall, while both apps have a strong base of satisfied users, Uber demonstrated a more favorable sentiment distribution and fewer complaints. These results emphasize the value of user feedback in identifying service weaknesses and guiding app improvements to stay competitive in the ride-hailing industry.

Positive

Figure 2: Uber Positive Reviews Word Cloud

Figure 3: Grab Positive Reviews Word Cloud

The word clouds show the most frequent term in positive reviews for Uber and Grab, as shown in Figures 2 and 3. For Uber, words like *service*, *good*, *ride*, and *experience* appear most often, highlighting user satisfaction with its smooth rides, reliable drivers, and overall service quality. Terms like *excellent*, *friendly*, and *professional* also reflect a strong positive perception. In Grab’s word cloud,

commonly used words include *service*, *driver*, *food*, *delivery*, and *order*, indicating praise for its multifunctional services, especially food delivery. Other terms including *easy*, *convenient*, and *helpful* suggest that users value Grab’s accessibility and variety of offerings. Both apps were commended for good service and driver quality, but Grab’s reviews more often emphasized its additional features beyond ride-hailing.

Negative

Figure 4: Uber Negative Reviews Word Cloud

Figure 5: Grab Negative Reviews Word Cloud

The word clouds show that both Uber and Grab receive frequent complaints about *drivers*, *cancellations*, *customer service*, *time*, and *refunds*. Uber reviews often highlight issues with *rides*, *charges*, and *fares*, suggesting frustration with pricing and trip management. In contrast, Grab reviews frequently mention *orders*, *food*, and *delivery*, indicating dissatisfaction with its food delivery service. While both apps share negative sentiment around wait times and support, Uber is more associated with scams and transparency, whereas Grab faces criticism for useless options and poor app updates, reflecting broader usability concerns.

Feature-Based Sentiment Analysis

Feature	Positive Mentions	Negative Mentions
Booking	35	37
Customer Support	35	35
Driver Availability	7	10
Driver Quality	28	28
GPS	21	19
Payment	36	49
Responsiveness	34	45

Table 1: Feature-Based Sentiment Analysis of Grab

Table 1 reveals that user experiences with Grab are mixed across key features. Booking and customer support received nearly equal positive and negative mentions, indicating inconsistent reliability. Payment and app responsiveness raised more concern, with users praising diverse options and smooth performance but also reporting glitches and delays. Driver quality showed a balanced split, reflecting varied rider experiences, while GPS was mostly accurate but occasionally unreliable. Driver availability had fewer mentions, with slightly more negative feedback. Overall, users appreciate Grab's convenience and functionality, but recurring issues in performance and support impact satisfaction. Addressing these weaknesses is essential for improving user experience and maintaining trust in a competitive market.

Feature	Positive Mentions	Negative Mentions
Booking	29	35
Customer Support	35	33
Driver Availability	5	4
Driver Quality	41	41

GPS	22	21
Payment	42	29
Responsiveness	30	38

Table 2: Feature-Based Sentiment Analysis of Uber

Table 2 shows that Uber received generally more favorable feedback across features. Driver quality and payment stood out, with high positive mentions, 41 and 42, respectively, suggesting user appreciation for service professionalism and reliable transactions. Customer support and booking showed mixed responses, while responsiveness had slightly more negative mentions, indicating occasional app lag. Driver availability had the fewest concerns, implying it is not a major issue for users. Compared to Grab, Uber's payment system appears more transparent, and users report a smoother experience overall. While technical issues like app responsiveness and GPS still exist, Uber demonstrates more consistent user satisfaction, especially in service quality and reliability.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study evaluated Grab and Uber user satisfaction using Google Play Store reviews and text mining. The two applications received mixed reviews, with Grab receiving more negative feedback, particularly about technical issues and support. Uber was complimented for improved performance and drivers, but there were concerns about pricing and availability. Overall, Uber provides more functionality, although Grab is more inexpensive and popular locally. It is recommended that future studies include reviews from other platforms (e.g., Apple App Store), consider multilingual reviews, extend the review timeframe, and explore the impact of specific features or updates. Integrating additional data sources, such as app ratings and usage data, is advised as well for a more comprehensive study.

REFERENCES

1. Md Saad, N. H., Mei Nie, F., & Yaacob, Z. (2023). *Exploring sentiment analysis of online food delivery services post COVID-19 pandemic: grabfood and foodpanda*. *Journal of Foodservice Business Research*, 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15378020.2023.2294406>
2. Froehlich, A. (2024, June 26). *7 reasons why mobile apps are important for your business*. *Search Customer Experience*. <https://www.techtarget.com/searchcustomerexperience/tip/7-reasons-why-businesses-need-mobile-apps>
3. *Grab Philippines*. (2022, September 2). *Our story | Grab PH*. *Grab*. <https://www.grab.com/ph/about/our-story/>
4. Hoenig, H. (2025, February 24). *The history of Uber*. *Investopedia*. <https://www.investopedia.com/articles/personal-finance/111015/story-uber.asp>
5. Davis, J. P. (2018, September 19). *The Real Story Behind Uber's Exit from Southeast Asia*. *INSEAD Knowledge*. <https://knowledge.insead.edu/entrepreneurship/real-story-behind-ubers-exit-southeast-asia>
6. Trymata, & Trymata. (2024b, October 18). *What is User Satisfaction? Definition, Metrics and Best Practices - Trymata*. *Trymata*. <https://trymata.com/blog/what-is-user-satisfaction/>
7. Gillis, A. S., & Barney, N. (2024, August 28). *What is sentiment analysis?* *Search Business Analytics*. <https://www.techtarget.com/searchbusinessanalytics/definition/opinion-mining-sentiment-mining>
8. *Papers with Code - Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA)*. (n.d.). <https://paperswithcode.com/task/aspect-based-sentiment-analysis>